

PREFERENCES OF FILIPINO AND FOREIGN COLLEGE STUDENTS TOWARDS ONLINE TRANSLATION TOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Technological advancement makes translation convenient due to the emergence of various translation tools. This Explanatory-Sequential study aims to determine the preference and the factors affecting the preference of Filipino and Foreign college students toward the Online Translation Tool. Likewise, it also aimed to identify if there is a significant difference between the respondents' choices. To acquire the data, the researchers used a survey conducted on 15 Filipino and foreign collegiate students enrolled in universities in Manila and a focus group discussion among 3 Filipino students. The transcribed data were analyzed using Thematic Analysis. Moreover, the results of the quantitative data revealed that Google Translate was the preferred Online Translation Tool of Filipino and Foreign students for the reason of accessibility, user-friendliness, and the tendency of users to brand bias. The reasons presented in quantitative data are strengthened by the themes identified in the qualitative data. The three prevailing themes of Brand Bias, Accessibility, and Accuracy constituted the central theme of User Friendliness. It was identified through the Chi-Square Test that there is no significant difference among respondents' preferences (0.345 P-Value) toward online Translation software.

Keywords: Online Translation Tools, Filipino College Students, Foreign College Students, Preference, Factors

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INTRODUCTION

Translation is a process requiring a thorough command of the input language and target language in terms of the branches of linguistics, in addition to a great deal of creativity and imagination. According to Wilson E. (2015), translation is a calculated art and considered as a delicate science as it requires in-depth investigation and awareness of one's culture. This is the reason why it is said to be more than just exchanging one language for another.

Translation services are vital in solving communication barriers and strengthening connections between different individuals. The need for it is becoming more important and desirable. In many domains of life, translation services helped in knowledge transfer and in empathic communication.

As technology progressed through the 20th century, translation became easier with the development of web-based translation tools. The use of these web-based translation tools made communication tasks efficient. These tools made the lives of people much better and hassle-free, especially that translation needs become rampant digitally. According to the study of Kucis V. & Selijan S. (2014), the usage of web-based translation tools was of significant assistance to students in optimizing the quality of their translation. Moreover, in the present age, translation quality and speed and consistent terminology are becoming the most important aspects of technical translation.

Web-based translation tools are also a big help in education. Translating literature from one language to another language results in a better understanding of a text and the language itself. Gerlic (2010: 112) mentioned that there were numerous electronic and computer tools that can be used in the education process as well as in training, for translators to enhance the quality, efficiency, and speed of translation, the most important characteristics of the contemporary translation product. The translation profession has undergone a metamorphosis since the turn of the last century, embracing the new information and communication knowledge and skills, and adapting to the usage of the modern multilingual technologies and e-learning.

Globalization opens an extensive opportunity in different aspects of human life. One of the great opportunities of globalization is the recognition of different languages around the world. Despite the recognition of language diversity, there is an existing communication barrier that hinders the communicator from understanding the context of a certain language. It includes the relationship of language to culture and bilingualism which results in misunderstanding and confusion in translating the input language into the target language. With this, the researchers came up with the idea to conduct research about the preferred Online Translation Tools of the Filipino and foreign college students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to know the Online Translation Tool preferences of Filipino and foreign college students from selected universities in the City of Manila. This study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the preference on online translation tools of:
 - a. Filipino college students
 - b. foreign college students
2. Is there a significant difference between the preference of Filipino and Foreign Students?
3. What are the factors affecting the preference of Filipino and Foreign students in Online Translation Tools?
4. What are the themes found in the preference of Filipino students?

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

Explanatory-Sequential Design is utilized in this study. It implies collecting and analyzing quantitative and qualitative data in two consecutive phases within one study. The order of analyzing the

data is from quantitative data to qualitative data wherein qualitative data support and strengthen the data presented in quantitative data.

Participants

The population of this study is Filipino and Foreign college students enrolled in selected universities in the City of Manila. The following universities are open to foreign-national students. The respondents of this study are composed of 15 Filipino and 15 foreign college students. Foreign students are referred to as learners from other nations who crossed territorial borders for the purpose of education. Meanwhile, Filipino students are characterized as those learners who are natural-born or naturalized Filipino residing in the Philippines. A purposive sampling technique is employed in this study whereas the respondents were selected based on the student's nationality and availability. In addition, this technique utilizes judgment in selecting cases based on a specific purpose. The technique allows the researcher to collect appropriate and useful data in order to address the problems of a study.

Data Gathering Procedure

To gather information needed to support the study, a researcher-made questionnaire was used that underwent validity and reliability. This instrument in this study has two parts. The initial part contains a checklist of 11 identified Online Translation tools synthesized from Williamson K. (n.d.) and Rapid API (2021). The second part of the instrument consists of a four-point Likert scale test where the respondents will indicate their level of agreement towards the statement related to the reason for their preferred online translation tools with reasons divided into four subscales namely quality, user-friendliness, accessibility, and brand bias.

Data Analysis

A descriptive association to the four-point Likert scale will be utilized to measure the respondents' agreement on their reason for their preferences for Online Translation Tools. It will start at numerical value 1 which is equivalent to 1.00 up to 1.49 rating scale and its verbal interpretation is "strongly disagree". It will be followed by a numerical value of 2 which is equivalent to a 1.50 to 2.49 rating scale at its verbal interpretation of "disagree". Next is a numerical value of 3 which is equivalent to a 2.50 to 3.49 rating scale and its verbal interpretation of "agree". Lastly is the numerical value of 4, it is equivalent to 3.50 to 4.00 with its verbal interpretation of "strongly agree".

Frequency count was used to count the preference of Filipino and Foreign college students. The distribution for each preference was determined through percentage computation. Moreover, the Chi-Square test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the preference of Filipino and Foreign college students. Meanwhile, the weighted mean is intended to identify the agreement of the respondents towards their reason for their Online Translation tool preference. In order to strengthen the quantitative data, the researchers conducted Focus Group Discussion and used thematic analysis to interpret data. Participants in the Focus Group Discussion were Filipino College Students who consistently use Online Translation Tools. The said participants are coming from the respondents of quantitative data.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the data gathered and organized together with the analysis and interpretation. The tables were given appropriate interpretations based on the corresponding results.

SOP 1.A. What is the preference on online translation tools of Filipino College Students?

Table 1. Preferred Online Translation Tools/Software Application of Filipino students.

Rank	Translation Tools	f	%
1	Google Translate	13	86.67
2	Babylon	1	6.67

2	Bing Translator	1	6.67
3	Free Dictionary	0	0.00
3	Yandex	0	0.00
3	PROMT Online Translator	0	0.00
3	iTranslate	0	0.00
3	Reverso	0	0.00
3	Memory Translation	0	0.00
3	Linguee	0	0.00
3	Translatedict	0	0.00
TOTAL		15	100.00

The table above presents the preferences of Filipino college students towards Online Translation tools. Google Translate prevailed over the 10 listed Online Translators. It is the most preferred by 13 Filipino respondents. On the other hand, Free Dictionary, Yandex, PROMT Online Translator, iTranslate, Reverso, Memory Translation, Linguee and Translatedict were revealed to be the least Online Translators. Google Translate has been identified by RapidAPI (2021), Williamson (n.d), Moberly (2018), Clifford et al. (2013), Lyons (2016), Shen (2010), & Niño A. (2020) as the top Online Translation software. Thus, Google Translate is the preferred online translation software of Filipino College users.

SOP 1.B. What is the preference on online translation tools of Foreign College Students?

Table 2. Preferred Online Translation Tools/Software Application of Filipino students.

Rank	Translation Tool	f	%
1	Google Translate	15	100.00
2	Free Dictionary	0	0.00
2	Bing Translation	0	0.00
2	Linguee	0	0.00
2	Reverso	0	0.00
2	Translatedict	0	0.00
2	Memory Translation	0	0.00
2	Babylon	0	0.00
2	PROMT Online Translator	0	0.00
2	iTranslate	0	0.00
2	Yandex	0	0.00
TOTAL		15	100.00

The table above reveals the Online Translation Tool commonly used by Foreign College Students. In the 10 listed Online Translation tools, 15 foreign respondents chose Google Translate. In contrast to that, the result revealed that all of the 10 remaining translation software was the least Online translation tool that most of the foreign students make use of. As the result of the study conducted by different researchers including RapidAPI (2021), Williamson (n.d.), Moberly (2018), Clifford et al. (2013), Lyons (2016), Shen (2010), and Niño A. (2020), Google Translate is the top-listed translation tools. Therefore, Google Translate is the preferred translation software of Foreign College users.

SOP 2. Is there a significant difference between the preference of Filipino and foreign Students?

Table 3. The difference between the preference of Filipino and foreign students

Variables	P-Valuez
Preference of Filipino and Foreign College Students	0.343

The table above presents the Chi-Test results for the difference between Filipino and Foreign College students' preference towards Online Translation tools. The results revealed that the P-Value is 0.343 which is greater than 0.05. Overall, the statistical results implied that there is no significant difference between the preferences of the respondents regarding Online Translation software. Thus, the researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis of the study. The results implied that the difference in races will not determine the preference for the use of online translation tools. This is in relevance to the study conducted by Lyons (2016) where Google Translate prevails as preferred Online Translation tools of respondents from different schools.

SOP 3. What are the factors affecting the preference of Filipino and Foreign students in Online Translation Tools?

Table 4. The reason of Filipino respondents towards their preference on Online Translation Tools.

Reason of Filipino College Students towards their preference of selected Online Translation tools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
It has the capability to check new words.	3.29	0.47	Agree
It has the capability to recognize unfamiliar words	3.07	0.62	Agree
It produces better translation.	3.00	0.55	Agree
It translates with good sentence structure	2.79	0.58	Agree
It is easy to use	3.64	0.50	Strongly Agree
It produces fast translation	3.50	0.52	Agree
It is convenient	3.64	0.50	Strongly Agree
It is easy to navigate	3.64	0.50	Strongly Agree
It is the most accessible in terms of search engine results	3.43	0.76	Agree
It is the most familiar online translation tool.	3.50	0.65	Agree
It is free of charge	3.57	0.76	Strongly Agree

The Table revealed that the respondents strongly agree upon items 5, 7 and 8 which indicated as “It is easy to use”, “It is convenient” and “It is easy to navigate”. This is followed by “It is free of charge” with 3.57 mean score. The third reason that the respondents agreed upon are “It produces fast translation” and “It is the most familiar online translation tool”. Thus, the Filipino college users are using Translation software due to its accessibility, user-friendliness and User tendency to brand bias. In relevance to the reasons identified with the use of the said translation tool, the study of Moberly in 2018 expounded that appearance and accessibility affects the choice of the users on Online Translation Tool. Similarly, the study of Niño A. (2020) mentioned that the ability of the Online Translation Tool to be accessed for free makes it easier and convenient to be used by language students of all levels. Google Translate is accessible and can be easily downloaded from different software which run in cellular phones and computers (Whitney, 2020). The reason why it is the most preferred translation tool was proven by Smith (2019). According to Smith, the benefit of online translators is that they save time, due to their ability to translate faster. Moreover, the tendency to brand bias is in congruence with the study of Shen (2010) and Munpru S. & Wuttikrikunlaya P., (2013). Whereas an Online Translation tool preference is highly influenced by its popularity which is referred to as Brand Bias. The popularity of the said tool was also considered as the main reason the Online Translation tool was preferred by users.

Table 5. The reason of foreign respondents towards their preference on Online Translation Tools.

Reason of Foreign College Students for their preference of selected Online Translation tools	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
It has the capability to check new words.	3.00	0.78	Agree
It has the capability to recognize unfamiliar words	2.93	0.73	Agree

It produces better translation.	3.00	0.88	Agree
It translates with good sentence structure	2.64	0.84	Agree
It is easy to use	3.57	0.85	Strongly Agree
It produces fast translation	3.57	0.85	Strongly Agree
It is convenient	3.50	0.85	Agree
It is easy to navigate	3.50	0.85	Agree
It is the most accessible in terms of search engine results	3.43	0.85	Agree
It is the most familiar online translation tool.	3.57	0.85	Strongly Agree
It is free of charge	3.57	0.85	Strongly Agree

Table 5 presents the set of reasons of foreign College Students towards their preference of selected Online Translation tool. There were 4 reasons that came up with the same result, (3.57 mean score), these reasons include, it is easy to use, it produces fast translation, it is the most familiar online translation tool, and it is free of charge. It is followed by “It is easy to navigate” and “It is convenient” with 3.50 mean score. The third prevailing reason with 3.43 mean score is “it is the most accessible in terms of search engine results”. Therefore, Foreign students are influenced by accessibility, user-friendliness, and tendency of user to brand bias. The results of the study related to accessibility is congruent with the findings of Moberly (2018), Niño (2020) and Whitney (2020). Subsequently, User-Friendliness is in relevance to the study of Smith (2019). While users’ tendency to brand bias is cited through the study of Shen (2010) and Munpru S. & Wuttikrikunlaya P., (2013)

SOP 4. What are the themes found out in the preference of Filipino students?

Figure 1. The diagram of the Themes identified through thematic analysis.

Filipino College students are trying to translate their input language into the target language. Hence, they are having a hard time in conveying the content of the input language into the target language. With this problem, Filipino college students tend to use online translation tools.

A brand's catchy name influences a user to use a certain translation tool. It is also referred to as name recall which is the tendency of consumers to patronize products and services due to users’ ability to remember. The respondents expounded that the familiarity of the translation’s name affects their preference on the use of such a tool. Respondent A claimed that “[translation tool] since yun yung familiar sa kin” and “narinig ko na nga sya before” affects the instances of why participants preferred to use an online translation. In relation to that, the popularity and commonality of a translation tool also affects Filipino respondents in their preference. A Respondent argued that since almost everyone uses an online translation, it also influences them to use a tool. Respondent C stated that “Because that’s the common actually, common na ginagawa ng marami”. The verbatim from the respondents is related with the Law of

Commonality which referred to as customers tendency to constantly strive to belong in some way (Ashway, 2016).

Subsequently, respondents cannot deny the fact that the popularity of online translation tools affects their preference. Whereas respondent B exclaimed that “*Ang laking impact po ng kilala na*” implied that popularity’s impact is significant in their choice towards online translation tools. This theme is relevant to the study of Shen (2010); Mulpri (2013); and Wuttikrikunlaya P. (2013) which agreed that the popularity of the said tool was also considered as the main reason why the tool was preferred by its users. Aside from that, the search engine results are also cited which contributes to a Filipino user's preference over an online translation tool. From the verbatim of Respondent A they stated that “*the first thing kunyare nag search ka via online ng translation tool ayun yung pipiliin mo*”. This code is related to the availability of Online Translation tools. Furthermore, these codes and verbatims exemplified the theme of users’ tendency to brand bias which captures popularity, its impact to preference and Search Engine results.

Due to the availability of the online translation tool, translation of input language to a target language becomes convenient. Where the online translation tools fit well with the respondent’s needs to translate the input language to target language. “*I prepared much yung [Online Translation Tool] kasi mas accessible kasi talaga sya eh*” stated by Respondent C. The respondents easily choose translation tools based on the familiar translation tools that they know because it is readily available and immediate result. “*Kaya nga tayo nagta-translate for us-for us to know the translation of a specific language we are trying to convert instantly*” stated by Respondent A. Aside from its availability, ease of access is one variable that the respondents considered in using online translation tools. In which it supports the statement of Respondent A “*Pero dahil nga easy to access, ayon yung ginamit namin*”. The aforementioned variables are strengthened by the study of Niño (2020) which determined that the availability of Online Translation Tool on the internet and available gadgets makes it convenient and accessible for users. “*Mas accessible*”, “*instantly*”, “*easy to access*” will form accessibility as a theme which perceives convenience that will help in referencing.

Through the conversation, respondents' preferred online translation tool is also affected by the tool’s accuracy. Similarly, it is strengthened by user referencing of translation results. Referencing is used to ascertain translated words, phrases or sentences. This is expounded by the verbatims of Respondent A about “*Vocabulary*” and Respondent B which stated that “*nagdedevelop sya ng vocabulary words. Nagpromote sya ng communication*”. The correctness of translated words enables the user to retain those words that helped them to improve communication.

The participants prefer certain translation tools because of their closest translation of the input language to the target language. Respondent A stated that “*yung may pinakamalapit na translation. Kasi yung naging result nung nag-translate tayo gamit yung [Translation Tool], ano siya, uhm, nakag-produce siya ng [accurate translation] nung mismong phrase na ti-na-translate natin*”. A direct or closest translation to the target language also related to the accurate words produced by an Online Translation tool. Respondent C expressed that “*may mga times talaga na natatranslate nya talaga into a right word.*” Additionally, a correct translated structure also affects a user’s preference to online translation. Codes such as “*nakapag-produce siya ng [accurate translation] na tama yung grammar*” express this idea. Moreover, these are relevant to the quality of translation produced by online translation tools. Respondent C stated that “*Quality*”, “*quality or the standard of translations*” and “*may quality [accurate] nga daw*” stated by respondent D respectively influenced their preference toward online translation tools. The aforementioned verbatims comprised “*Accuracy*” as one of the prevailing themes in the analysis.

Moreover, Filipino students' preference is affected by Online Translation Tools features that are easily manipulated. It is supported by Respondent C in which she stated “*Compromised yung features pero mas marami siya [design, format, buttons]*” and “*mas marami siyang feature*”. While Respondents A states “*mas madali nga naman pong i-manipulate, pwede ka gumamit ng voice*” and “*Mag-ta-type yon ng kusa*”. The code according to the statement of Respondent A talks about the features that an online translation tool has. Features are also shown on the codes found on the statement of Respondent B which is “*mayro n siyang text, conversation, yung mga type ng languages*”. Features, easily manipulated, easy to use anchored

on the theme user-friendliness. Thus, user-friendliness helps the users to save time due to its ability to translate faster (Smith, 2019).

The user tendency to brand bias, accessibility and accuracy comprised the theme user-friendliness. For an instance, Respondent B stated *“As you can see do’n sa [Online Translation Tool], mayro’n siyang text, conversation, at yung mga type ng language”* where in conversation, and type of languages are part of online translation tools that will help referencing data. In which referencing is the underlying variable that connects accuracy and accessibility. In relevance to that, users have the tendency to double-check the translation to improve their communications. This is exemplified by respondent B which states that *“nagdedevelop sya ng vocabulary words. Nagpo-promote sya ng communication”*. Consequently, their referencing contributes to user-system communications that connect accuracy and brand bias. User-system communication is a process of Translation tool such as Google Translate to improve quality of translation based on the number of translations made in the tool Karami (2014). While the statement of Respondent C *“I much preferred [Online Translation Tool] because that’s the common actually, common na ginagawa ng marami ... and mas marami siyang feature.”* The codes *“common”* and *“feature”* are part of the availability which links tendency to brand bias and the accessibility of online translation tools.

CONCLUSION

In accordance with the indicated findings this research therefore concluded that Google Translate is the most preferred online translation software of Filipino and Foreign collegiate students citing that this software is accessible through the internet which is also the top most result if being searched using search engine websites such as Google. It is also a major factor that this tool does not consume a long time for translation results to come out whereas this software does not charge users for translation. Likewise, it also offers users numerous languages to choose for a translation. Moreover, the said translation tool has appealing and comprehensible features which users can navigate efficiently with minimal or without assistance. It also loads fast which consumes lite internet speed. The results revealed that there is no significant difference between the preference of Filipino and Foreign College students toward Online Translation Tools. Google has been a familiar brand for most users across the globe because it offers numerous, free, and online-based software intended for a number of functions. Hence, its popularity can contribute to the respondent’s choice. Aside from that, it has features that are accessible, easy to navigate and offers a variety of languages for translation. This is further supported by the findings through the themes identified which are Tendency to Brand Bias, Accessibility, and Accuracy. These three prevailing themes constituted User-Friendliness as a central theme. Thus, the reasons cited in foreign studies are congruent with the reasons determined in the thematic analysis for Filipino students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations for Schools, Teachers, learners, and Future Researchers are proposed based on the findings of the study:

1. It is recommended for Schools and Educators to apply and use Google Translate in courses that need translation to aid and improve learner’s language learning.
2. The researchers, therefore, recommend that Filipino college students use Google translate as an online translation tool for their studies. The result of this study further determined that Google translate is an accessible and convenient tool for Filipino students for immediate translation. On the other hand, the researchers also recommend the result of this study to foreign college students who have a hard time translating word. The result further suggests that Google translate is also the preference of foreign college students.
3. Due to the limited number of respondents present in this research, it is highly recommended that future researchers administer the same topic to a larger number of respondents. In addition, it is also recommended to conduct Focus group discussions with Foreign College students to subsequently strengthen current findings of their reasons for preference.
4. It is suggested for future researchers to focus on the disadvantages and advantages of using the use Online Translation tool in the field of language learning. Furthermore, it is highly recommended to

future researchers to delve deeper into the accuracy or the quality of Translation produced by Online Translation Software as this is one of the key findings of this research in thematic analysis.

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